

**SCRIPT ANALYSIS OF A ONE-MAN THEATRE: A PLAYWRIGHT'S
CHALLENGE IN MBAJIORGU'S *THE PRIME MINISTER'S SON*
BY**

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Scripts are peculiar in that they are paradoxically both complete and unrealized, Inasmuch as they tell stories, create their own distinct fictional worlds, and develop identifiable characters, they are complete pieces of literature....they are composed for the purpose of providing a basis for a play to take place on a stage before a gathered audience.

Plays require planning, a requirement usually met by scripting. In this sense, scripts are unrealized plays... Playwrights write with a stage in mind, and we must read them with a *theatre in our head*... (Longman, 1)

Introduction

Contemporary Nigerian society has continued to be bombarded with a wealth of artistic and literary experimentations in recent time. These Experiments are either structurally, stylistically cally or linguistically inclined. Between Ola Rotimi, Femi Osofisan and Wale Ogunyemi, to Hyginus Ekwuazi, Tunde Fatunde and Sonny Sampson-Akpan, the drumbeat has sounded the sarme; finding a suitable and comfortable medium of getting messages across to the Nigerian populace, majority of whom are starkly unlettered. While Femi Osofisan continues to experiment with literary forms Und techniques and has,

in fact, earned for himself the accolade - "Master of Literary Experiments" (MLE), others appear to have been satisfied in their search and seem resolved, differently and complacently, to settle for such results.

Some new experiments are being tested on the contemporary Nigerian literary scene. One of them is Greg Mbajorgu's *The Prime Minister's Son*, a one-actor play. Apart from Sonny Sampson-Akpan's *Comments*, an experiment also, in a one-actor drama, Mbajorgu's *The Prime Minister's Son* is, perhaps, the second known published one-actor play. And if this tested actor-playwright continues on this line (as he is wont to), he would be blazing this trail for others to follow. This is because, since Sampson-Akpan's publication of *Comments*, over twenty years ago, the playwright (Akpan) appears to have lost interest in plunging further into the precarious Nigerian waters of play publication. Only recently, a young, budding and promising Nigerian playwright and man of many parts, Ben Binebal, appears to have also been attracted to this artistic fancy. His latest play, "My Life in the Burning Creeks" (already in press), is also a one-actor drama on the struggles of the oppressed people of the oil-rich Niger Delta who have been thrown into abject squalor consequent upon the exploitative tendencies of mega rich oil companies with legal and physical backings from the Nigerian Government. Intrigues among brethren of the Niger Delta extractions are played out as each tries to outwit the other in a game of dog- eat-dog, with the winner taking it all. The intrigues become necessary in an attempt by smart brethren of the Niger Delta decent to grab the little crumbs that fall from the table of the rich oil companies (in the form of gratifications) in their attempt, through divide and rule, to buy over a select few loyalists. It is important to emphasize that these essayists recognize the pioneering efforts of earlier actor lone-rangers (who performed as one-man actors) in the Nigerian society like the famed endeavours of Funsho Alabi of the "I have a Dream" fame, in his attempt to resurrect, artistically, the famous speech of that American activist, Martin Luther King Jnr. whose famous speech radically revolutionized the American society, leading to his assassination at his prime; the efforts of Sonny Oti, Innocent Ohiri, Tunji Sotimirin and a host of others cannot also be wished away in a hurry. These actors distinguished themselves as one-man actors in different parts of the Nigerian society. However, our emphasis in this essay is on scripted and published one-man plays since it is on this that our analysis will be based.

The Actor as Co-Creator in the Theatre

The cardinal task of any actor in the course of any given production is the ability to give convincing meaning to character playing through role interpretation. In the word of Thompson, (2) "the actor is expected to carry the role he is to play, and do what the character is supposed to do in the most convincing style. Thus, the actor would have to subsume *himself* into the character such that the audience who knows him real life would not see any semblance of him whether on stage or in film". It becomes pellucid from the above assertion that the art of the actor transcends mere play. Wright, (2) insists that the acting profession "involves hard work and serious vocal, physical and mental training" while Wilson, (92) conceives it as a "difficult, demanding profession... it calls for arduous training and preparation"

An actor, no doubt, is a co-creator of role in the course of a production in the theatre. While he submits himself for use as a willing instrument to the theatre director in the process of role creation, it is expected of him to fill in certain physical and emotional details, tapping from his inner recesses or personal experiences. While the theatre director generates ideas that are intended to make the process of character interpretation easy, plausible and convincing, the actor, necessarily feels those ideas, internalizes and realizes them in the physical form, through his body, intellect and voice, thus presenting verisimilitude before a given audience. The actor must, of necessity, reach out to the audience. Everything about him must communicate since it is through him that the playwright's message is transmitted to the audience. Little wonder, then, that a foremost acting theorist and performer, Fernald, (65) defines acting as "communication, the discovery of a truth implicit in an author's words..." Johnson's explications on Fernald's view above is quite instructive and informing;

The process of discovering *a truth implicit in an author's words* is one of the preliminary duties... that the actor does, under the guidance of the director. To discover implies that there must be a search for it. An actor searches, as it were, for an understanding of the author's truth, Reading, re-reading, querying, reasoning, etc, are all "tasky tasks" employed by the actors and their director in discovering the truth in a text.... Having discovered the truth, interpreting that truth and giving it a direction or focus, another experience altogether. (21-22)

From the foregoing, it becomes patent that in terms of script analysis, the expectations and demands on the one-man actor are myriad. Only he appears on the stage for thirty minutes or more, entering and playing different roles and his artistry and finesse are expected to hold the audience spell-bound else he presents himself as an unskilled artist. In the course of his presentation, he may be required to;

...play gods, demons, animals, ghosts, machines, kings, queens, fairies, elves. They have been challenged to appear as mutes, amputees, transsexuals; to be twice or half their age or more and sometimes both within the same play, and to play as if differently gendered, or with a sexual orientation different from their own. Actors must be seen to live in centuries different from their own, and to practice professions different from those for which they have been trained; they must credibly seem to worship deities and spirits different from those they personally believe in, and to adhere to philosophies different from those they personally practice; finally, they must perform acts, and feel emotions, radically different from those they have ever done or felt in their entire real world" lives. (Cohen, xii)

For a group or collaborative acting, the above may be easier, but for a lone actor, the process of transforming from one role to the other and being able to sustain the cardinal character in the drama is tasking, demanding and requires some form of artistic dexterity. Mbajiorgu's *The Prime Minister's Son*, requires such artistic dexterity from a prospective performer because of the different roles and situations created by the playwright in which the lone actor is expected to operate and function,

A Playwright's Attempt and Challenge: Towards a Script Analysis of *The Prime Minister's Son*

Greg Mbajiorgu's experiment in *The Prime Minister's Son* is, no doubt, a commendable effort. The play had toured for eight years before the publishers finally picked it up. When in 1991 Mbajiorgu first directed and acted the play for "James Ene Henshaw, Kalu Uka and Meki Nzewi at the NYSC Secretariat, Calabar" (p. vii), one of these essayists was present. In fact, the essayist (who was present during the performance) was, then, the

Cross River State's Director of the NYSC (National Youths Service Corps) Drama Troupe which. (in collaboration with the University of Calabar) successfully performed Femi Osolisan's *Who's Afraid of Solarin?* and a number of other skits.

Mbajiorgu got his play published in an age that does not encourage talents due to the prohibitive cost of publication. This age, ironically laments the lack of scripted plays and creative drive and ingenuity among young talents. Without any scintilla of doubt, the Nigerian society is blessed with a crop of talented writers whose works cannot be published for financial reasons. The pocket, nowadays, determines what is published with the dire consequence that excellence is, more often than not, sacrificed for mediocrity, those who have the money get published, no matter the shoddy nature of their creative efforts, while those who actually possess the creative drive but cannot afford the cost of production have their works shelved or rejected. Also, actors are lacked the opportunity of putting into good use their God-given talents for lack of good scripts to experiment with. *The Prime Minister's Son* will, no doubt, be a long-awaited relief to many a good actor while Binebai's *"My Life in the Burning Creeks"* is also being eagerly awaited.

No doubt, Mbajiorgu has delved into a difficult and demanding aspect of creative dramaturgy. Attempts by young actors to try themselves out on one-man dramatic pieces are frequently limited to short, humorous and undocumented sketches which are usually performed during variety shows in institutions and during functions and other social gatherings. In a manner similar to the famed one-actor crusader, Funsho Alabi, or the promising Hafez Oyetoro, Mbajiorgu plunges into a difficult artistic terrain of a one-man production. The fifty-eight page play tells the pathetic story of a young, hapless boy whose moon was destined never to shine. He was born into penury, grew up in suffering and just as the truth of his paternity is revealed to him (he is the unfortunate product of an unholy alliance between a Prime Minister and his house help of a mother), he is rejected by his own father. He thus goes about the world, a wanderer, bemoaning his fate.

The story of *The Prime Minister's Son* could be divided into two parts: part one could be tagged the "narration scenes" while the second part the "action scenes". By the expression, "narration scenes", we refer to those sections of the play where the Prime Minister's son simply relates his travails to his audience in story form employing prose narrative, while the action

scenes" are those scenes where he attempts to capture, through dialogue, character creation, gesticulations, voice variation, stage businesses and the like, his different ordeals. The latter is re-lived on pages 13-20-21, 26-27,30-38,40-41, 43-45 and 50-51. In all, there are about twenty-eight pages of such "scenes" - about half of the text. The other half of the text is devoted to narration.

We want to recall, very lucidly, that when *The Prime Minister's Son* was first staged in Calabar, one of the potent criticisms against it was its overwordiness and its rather insipid prosaic style of presentation. Reading through the now published text, it is obvious that Mbajiorgu has endeavoured, in his own way, to live bits. In a play that is expected to build in more "action scenes" even in the to sustain an audience's interest for up to an hour on stage, (with the audience watching just one lone actor), we believe, and strongly too, that the young playwright still has a lot to inject into the play in case of a possible re-print. Perhaps, a borrowing from literary experiments of the pre-Independence South African society would have aided Mbajiorgu in this aspect. While experimenting with the most minimal number of characters (for obvious reasons anyway) in plays like Athol Fugard's *Woza Albert* or Matsemela Manaka's *Egoli* (plays of two characters each), to mention but a few, one remarks the creative ingenuity of those playwrights who know that to allow a character to rant on prosaically for upward of seven pages or even more without accompanying sufficient stage businesses would be tantamount to attempting an artistic hara-kiri. Actions are thus speedily and easily varied with diverse in-built situations to allow for dexterity and role-reversal on the part of the actor(s) on the one hand, and imagined scene mutations on the part of the audience on the other. Apart from this device helping to stretch the imagination of the audience, it also helps to carry them along. In other words, it serves as an audience-involving device. Borrowing is not a crime in a creative venture. Funsho Alabi or Hafez Oyetero know when to stop a narration and go into action. Mbajiorgu himself appears to know this, at least, in theory, for he states in his introductory notes thus:

This Drama is peculiar in the sense that it is designed for a single actor who changes frequently from one character to another, dramatised narrative to dramatised dialogue. For this lone actor to successfully sustain the required performance tempo, swift character changes are mandatory (p. vii) But how effectively has Mbajiorgu succeeded in helping his lone actor to sustain an audience's interest with his style of writing? The playwright may have

attempted to carry his audience along by certain in-built devices as evident in his employment of certain expressions like "my friends, my country men" (p. 3), "my people" (p. 47) and so on. These expressions are, in themselves, jejune, hackneyed and trite and they have the tendency to bore, not to excite an audience. Many of such expressions abound in the play. Perhaps, the playwright would have been more successful if he had tried to versify some of those narrative speeches like he did at the end of the play. This, at least, would have made him more conscious of the effective use of dramatic pauses, action-packed lines and other punctuational devices which are of necessity to a venture of this nature.

The "action scenes" can also be better effectively realised. As those scenes stand for now, some of the situations created are not serious in intents. The playwright, buries, as it were, some of the significant action scenes under prose narration without effective supportive pauses and adequate situations that could create room for role-reversals. By far, the most effective scene in the "action scenes" is found in Emenike, re-living the sad story of his wretched past before Ezinma (pp. 30-38). Even at that, the playwright does not appear to understand the character he has created in Emenike as the illiterate househelp and gardener to the Prime Minister oscillates between pidgin and Queen's English and really not too certain of when to use what. There is also a contradiction in the character portrayal of the Prime Minister. The playwright presents him to his audience as an ex member of parliament, who was rarely found in the midst of ordinary people (p. 14) and simultaneously as a man who has a soft spot for common people" (p. 36). The playwright then intrudes into the thought flow of the Prime Minister's son converting him, in the process, to a philosopher and a social commentator (pp. 56-58) as the play reaches its zenith. Here, we hear, not the voice of the Prime Minister's son, but that of Mbajiorgu, reeling out a catalogue of woes that have befallen our hapless society in the not-too-distant past. The usual Nigerian syndrome of "thank Godism" or "e go better is brought into the fore in this scene to encourage our pertinacious and enduring sense. The playwright's projected philosophy (which, I think, he wants his reader or audience to embrace), is, 'no matter how bad, we are not worse off.'

On the positive side, we dare to advance the thesis that the playwright's treatment of his cardinal theme the plight of the common man

through the lens of the Prime Minister's son deserves some commendation. In one breath, Mbajiorgu takes a swipe at the run of unfolding events in the society and bids us ask ourselves how proper it is for dogs to start feeding on their own flesh. It is our conviction that the play, as it is, would have been more successful as a novelette. This is because the playwright has not created effective dramatised narrative scenes to help the actor to realise himself and his creative potentials. *The Prime Minister's Son*, captures the sad and grim realities of our time. To that extent, it is of utmost germaneness. As Renate Albertson-Marton said, it (the play) is a very moving piece" (See the blurb of the text). We agree with him because it is obvious that the playwright was bent on making the Prime Minister's son to suffer. We were going to add that Mbajiorgu, (through his play), presents himself as a pessimist of repute who believes that nothing good could come out of his society but the consoling and admonishing morality at the end of the play calls for a re-think:

Why should we live in this world
In this way:
Human beings living like slaves
With their fate in the hands of fellow men?
Why...? Why...? Why...? (p. 58)

In all, Mbajiorgu's artistic effort spoils for a challenge. Aspiring playwrights could borrow from him because the young and upcoming writer is ravishing a virgin literary field from which the Nigerian society stands to benefit.

Conclusion

Longman, (1) has advanced the argument that;

... Scripts operate in a context. What is on the page relates to what will be on the stage, and what is on stage relates to the audience gathered in the house, and the whole of the theatrical experience relates to the world beyond the confines of the theatre, to the human experience. No play works in a vacuum.

Mbajiorgu's *The Prime Minister's Son* finds its relevance in the politics of systemic elimination, occasioned by selfishness and grab of a minority few, over the majority of the Nigerian people. If, in the words of Sir John Van Burgh, in his prologue to *The Provoked Wife* (cited in Thompson, 7), that "it is the intent and business of the stage, to copy out the follies of the age, to hold to every man a faithful glass and show man of what species he is, an ass, then *The Prime Minister's Son* has succeeded as dramatic literature. It is also a known fact that drama transcends the ordinariness of literature to embrace performance or play production. In fact, this is the singular, distinguishing attribute of drama and the famed dictum that no drama can be considered worthy of its name except it has seen the light of the stage (in performance) is as real as death. The dictum is axiomatic and it is in consonance with Majorie Boulton's opinion that "a play is not really a piece of literature for reading. A true play is three-dimensional, it is literature that walks and talks before our eyes... the text of the play is meant to be translated into sights, sounds and actions which occur literally and physically on a stage" (See Thompson, 16-17). The challenge in a one-actor theatre therefore rests, also on the actor. He needs his imagination and intellect to fill in the gaps left unattended to by the playwright. He needs his body and voice to facilitate the process of communication. The voice must necessarily possess rhythm and colour if it must function as an effective accompaniment to action and other stage businesses. Schanker and Ommanney (61) have submitted that for correct speech and voice production, it is necessary for you to have deep central breathing; an open, relaxed throat: flexible tongue and lips; and a relaxed lower jaw" This is especially true in a one-actor theatre like Mbajiorgu's *The Prime Minister's Son*. In a situation where an actor reels out narrations, voice inflexions are of utmost necessity. An actor with a flat, colourless voice will not do artistic justice to *The Prime Minister's Son* because of its duration and length.

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